

Are Islamic Windows of Conventional Banks Still Relevant in the Landscape of Islamic Banking?

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the factors contributing to the rise of Islamic windows and their consequences on the Islamic banking sector by utilizing the literature on Islamic windows. The study identifies four main factors viz. legal, economic, strategic and organizational capability that motivate conventional banks to operate Islamic windows. The growth of Islamic windows has driven competition, encouraging both Islamic banks and Islamic windows to innovate and improve service offerings that led to the development of hybrid financial products and new investment solutions.

ملخص

تستكشف هذه الدراسة العوامل التي ساهمت في ظهور النوافذ الإسلامية وتداعياتها على قطاع الصيرفة الإسلامية، باستخدام الأدبيات المتعلقة بالنوافذ الإسلامية. وتحدد الدراسة أربعة عوامل رئيسة تحفز البنوك التقليدية إلى تشغيل نوافذ إسلامية، وهي: العوامل القانونية والاقتصادية والاستراتيجية والقدرات المؤسسية. ودفع نمو النوافذ الإسلامية المنافسة، مما شجع كلا من البنوك الإسلامية والنوافذ الإسلامية على الابتكار وتحسين جودة الخدمات المقدمة، الأمر الذي أسفر عن تطوير منتجات مالية هجينة وحلول استثمارية جديدة.

RESUME

Cette étude explore les facteurs contribuant à l'essor des guichets islamiques et leurs conséquences sur le secteur bancaire islamique en s'appuyant sur la littérature relative aux guichets islamiques. L'étude identifie quatre facteurs principaux, à savoir les capacités juridiques, économiques, stratégiques et organisationnelles, qui motivent les banques conventionnelles à exploiter des guichets islamiques. La croissance des guichets islamiques a stimulé la

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concurrence, encourageant à la fois les banques islamiques et les guichets islamiques à innover et à améliorer leurs offres de services, ce qui a conduit au développement de produits financiers hybrides et de nouvelles solutions d'investissement.

Keywords: Islamic windows, full-fledged Islamic banks, Islamic subsidiaries of conventional banks, *riba*, usury.

JEL Classification: F39; G1; G2; G20; G21

1. Introduction

Islamic banking industry has experienced tremendous growth over the years, expanding not only in nations with majority Muslim populations, but also in countries where Muslims are a minority. According to the ICD-LSEG Islamic Finance Development Report 2023, the assets of the world's Islamic banks expanded rapidly from USD 1.3 trillion in 2012 to reach USD 3.24 trillion by end of 2022, and the number of full-fledged Islamic banks rose by 36% to 336 in 2022 while conventional banks with Islamic windows or services increased by 84% to 274 in 2022 (ICD-LSEG, 2023). Ironically, despite some concerns being raised on the permissibility and legitimacy of Islamic windows from the shariah perspective, the above data suggests a significant increase in the number of Islamic windows compared to full-fledged Islamic banks within the last decade. This raises the question as to what triggers the significant surge in Islamic banks.

Although there has been a considerable deal of scholarly attention on Islamic windows as evidenced by the sharp rise in publications, they tend to focus on whether Islamic windows set up by conventional banks are permissible from the shariah perspective (Mustafa, 2022; Salh, 2019) and the performance of Islamic windows in terms of efficiency, profitability and customers' perception compared to their full-fledged Islamic bank counterparts (see e.g. Ghroubi and Khalifa, 2025; Al-Asmi et al., 2024; Ali and Hailu, 2022; Shabbir, et al., 2020; Al-Ismaili, 2018). However, there is a gap in the literature discussing the possible reasons for the increased popularity of Islamic windows and their impact on the sector.

Hence, the aim of this paper is to contribute to the extant literature on Islamic windows of conventional banks by exploring on the possible factors contributing to the significant growth in the number of Islamic

windows and their consequence on the Islamic banking industry. It will specifically focus in answering the following questions, *viz.* what are the options available in establishing Islamic banking and the views of shariah scholars on the operation of Islamic windows; what motivates conventional banks in setting up Islamic windows; and what are the consequences of growth in Islamic windows on the Islamic banking industry.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the conversion process to Islamic banking, followed by discussion on the differences in opinions on the permissibility of Islamic windows among shariah scholars in section 3. Section 4 presents the motivations of conventional banks in setting up Islamic windows while section 5 highlights the consequences of Islamic windows for the Islamic banking sector. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Islamic banking - conversion options and features

2.1 The rise of Islamic financial institutions

Commercial activities are highly regarded in Islam, and Muslims, besides fulfilling their religious duties, are encouraged to propagate Islamic economic activities worldwide as stated in the *Qur'an* (Al-Jumu'ah 62: 9-10).² Management and disposal of resources truthfully help believers to fulfill their covenant with God which is to act as His *khalifah*³ (vicegerent) including as temporary trustee of all His resources on this earth⁴. Hence, in the post-independent states of the Muslim world in the 1960s, developing economic activities that conform to Islamic teachings was on top of the agenda. Given the important role of financial institutions in the

² "O believers! When the call to prayer is made on Friday, then proceed 'diligently' to the remembrance of Allah and leave off 'your' business. That is best for you, if only you knew (9). Once the prayer is over, disperse throughout the land and seek the bounty of Allah. And remember Allah often so you may be successful (10)".

³ The Qur'an states: "Behold, thy Lord said to the angels: 'I will create a vicegerent on earth.' They said: 'Wilt thou place therein one who will make mischief therein and shed blood?' Whilst we do celebrate Thy praises and glorify Thy holy (name)?". He said: "I know what ye know not" (Al-Baqarah 2:30).

⁴ The Qur'an states: "Believe in Allah and His Messenger, And spend (in charity) out of the (substance) whereof He has made you Heirs. For, those of you who believe and spend (in charity) – for them is a great reward" (Al-Hadid 57:7).

economic system, efforts were made in the 1970s to align the financial sector with Islamic teachings that led to the emergence of Islamic financial institutions (IFIs) that integrates religious principles with economic activities (Napier and Haniffa, 2011).

IFIs obtain their legitimacy by distinguishing themselves from their conventional counterparts based on their underlying principles of complying with *shariah* (Islam rulings), which makes it attractive to Muslims (Gambling et al., 1993). *Shariah* prohibits undertaking activities that involve interest (*riba*)⁵, gambling (*maysir*), speculative transactions where the subject matter and outcome of which are unknown or uncertain (*gharar*), as well as dealing in prohibited (*non-halal*) and unethical activities and financial transactions. However, the emergence and evolution of IFIs are to a large extent influenced by the dynamics of political and socio-economic circumstances within as well as beyond Muslim countries. Consequently, over time, the implicit and explicit intentions and goals changed and affected the nature and structure of IFIs that exist today.

2.2 Structure of IFIs

The financial sector is a highly regulated sector and financial institutions have to abide to the country's legal system and regulations related to banking and supervision. The establishment of a new IFI or conversion of a conventional bank may require changes to the country's existing banking and tax law to accommodate the *shariah* requirements. There are three conversion options process available to existing conventional banks for consideration in entering the Islamic banking sector. This section discusses each of those options including the main features and potential challenges of each option.

a) Full conversion (Full-fledged Islamic banks)

The first option is a full conversion to an Islamic bank or also known as a full-fledged Islamic bank. This is a standalone Islamic bank offering a full range of products and services and may include Islamic investment banking activities, such as underwriting sukuk issuances or managing Shariah-compliant investment and hedge funds, or to manage its own

⁵ There are four verses in the Qur'an condemning *riba*. The other three verses beside the above are Al-Imran 3:130, An-Nisa 4:161 and Ar-Rum 30:39.

treasury and money market operations (Sole, 2007). The products and services offered must all be approved by the shariah supervisory committee/board and the accounting system are set up to capture the unique Islamic contract transactions⁶ according to the accounting standard adopted⁷.

A full conversion signals the bank's firm commitment to operate under Shariah principles, thus enhancing its credibility. However, some of the key challenges of such conversion include: (i) regulation of the country may not license the operation of full-fledged Islamic banks; (ii) high operating costs as this may involve changing the internal structure and system, training of employees and also volatility in income stream due to the nature of transactions being based on participation, profit-sharing and speculation; and (iii) exposure to competition in the niche market with other full-fledged Islamic banks as well as Islamic subsidiary of conventional banks and Islamic windows.

b) Islamic subsidiaries of conventional banks

The second option is to open an Islamic subsidiary of the conventional bank. As a separate entity, it has autonomous decision making and can offer the full-range of core banking products and services similar to its conventional parent but are shariah-compliant with the terminologies changed, and also the range of products typically offered by full-fledged Islamic banks. All the products offered must be approved by the shariah supervisory committee/board and the treasury is separate from the parent and is managed independently. The accounting system is built to capture all the transactions for preparation of the subsidiary's financial statements and feed into the parent's accounting system for preparation of Group Consolidated Financial Statements.

⁶ This includes financial products such as trade with margin (*Murābahah*), forward sales and manufacturing contracts (*Salam and Istisnā*), profit and loss sharing partnerships (*Mudhārabah/Musyārahah*), rent with rental charges (*Ijārah*), and fee-based services (*Wakālah*), each of which requires specific accounting treatment.

⁷ IFIs may adopt either the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) or the Islamic Accounting and Reporting Standards issued by the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI).

The advantage of opening a subsidiary is that the parent bank may continue servicing its conventional customers, while the subsidiary expands its Islamic activities in clear separation from the conventional business. Some of the key challenges of such conversion include: (i) higher set-up cost compared to Islamic windows as it is a separate entity; (ii) it needs to align with the parent its share of profit and loss; and (iii) higher credibility risk compared to full-fledged since one of the main concern that arises is that the subsidiary's initial capital may be Islamically unacceptable as the funds provided by the parent bank is not guaranteed to originate from Islamic compliant sources as it involves interest taking and giving (see Abd Rahman, 2006, and Yaquby, 2005). However, a possible solution to this is for the subsidiary to commit to making future charitable donations as a way to purify the original funds (Sole, 2007). This option is popular in countries where regulation does not permit for operation of full-fledged Islamic banks or when conventional banks are confident in meeting the diverse needs of clientele with varying Islamic and ethical commitments as well as socioeconomic backgrounds (Delle Foglie et al., 2023).

c) Islamic windows

The third option is to operate an Islamic window. Definitions of Islamic windows vary with some referring to branches of conventional banks with their operations following the requirements of Islamic law and specializing in Islamic financial transactions (Al-Murtan, 2005; Shehata, 2001) while others refer to independent units or branches dedicated to selling Islamic products and services under the supervision of specialized Shariah authority responsible for ensuring compliance with Islamic principles (Sebaa and Khan, 2021; Salh, 2019; Hani-Mohamed, 2017). The Islamic banking regulator, IFSB (2007, p.12), defined Islamic window as:

“...part of a conventional financial institution (which may be a branch or dedicated unit of that institution) that provides both fund management (investment accounts) and financing and investment that are Shari`ah-compliant. In principle, these windows are potentially self-contained in terms of Shari`ah-compliant financial intermediation, as the funds managed will be invested in Shari`ah compliant assets...”

In some jurisdictions, Islamic windows refer to an operation whereby an institution invests funds in shariah-compliant assets without such funds being mobilised specifically for shariah-compliant investment purposes and the operations may be carried out through either branches that offer current account facilities or other units of the institution. However, IFSB does not recognize such operation as an Islamic window. Given the popularity of Islamic windows in many jurisdictions, IFSB require institutions offering Islamic windows to have their internal systems, procedures and controls providing reasonable assurance that: (a) the transactions and dealings of the windows are in compliance with shariah rules and principles; and (b) appropriate risk management policies and practices are followed.

Islamic windows do not have independent structure as final decisions are made by the conventional management team and the accounting system will capture the transactions to feed into the preparation of the Financial Statements of the conventional bank. The financial performance of Islamic window is normally shown separately in the Notes to the Account. This option may be suitable for conventional banks interested in probing the potential of this market by taking advantage of its existing branch network to reach potential new clientele. Some key challenges for Islamic windows include deciding on the range of products to offer, and since it operates under the umbrella of its host, its credibility risk is higher than Islamic subsidiary as there is bound to be comingling of *halal* and *haram* sources of funds.

Table 1 presents a summary of the key features of the three options of conversion available to conventional or traditional banks to consider if they wish to enter the Islamic banking sector.

Table 1:Comparative summary of the three Islamic banking business models

Features	Full-fledged Islamic banks	Islamic subsidiaries of conventional banks	Islamic windows of conventional banks
Banking structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Islamic management team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate Islamic management team. Autonomous decision making as an independent identity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional management team where business decisions are made. Head of Islamic Banking Windows reports directly to the conventional bank's CEO.
System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Islamic core banking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional core banking with terminologies changed and enhancement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional core banking with terminologies changed and enhancement.
Document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on shariah content. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on shariah content. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancement to shariah content.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shariah based. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify shariah touch-points to enhance process (leverage) – shariah-compliant. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify shariah touch-points to enhance process (leverage) – shariah-compliant.
<i>Aqad</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design based on Islamic contracts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design based on Islamic contracts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design based on Islamic contracts.
Treasury	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Islamic treasury structure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate structure and managed independently. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate structure and managed independently.
Accounting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General ledger for Islamic transactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate ledgers built and flow through different books. Separate Financial Statements by subsidiary. Consolidation of financial statements only in banking group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate ledgers built and flow through different books. Statement of Financial Position discloses Islamic Banking Window performance as part of the Notes to the Account.
Key challenge(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High operating cost Competition Regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alignment with parent. Higher set-up cost. Credibility risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Range of products and services to offer. Credibility risk.

Source: Adapted from Islamic banking windows | Islamic Bankers Resource Centre

3. Legitimacy of Islamic windows

Shariah scholars and Islamic bankers are split regarding the issue of permissibility and legitimacy of Islamic windows. They can be categorised into three groups (Shahzad & Hameed, 2018): those who totally opposed, those who support under conditional circumstances, and those who are totally supportive of Islamic windows.

a) Opponents of Islamic windows

Those who oppose Islamic windows have questioned the strategic motive of conventional banks and viewed their involvement in Islamic windows being just another way to deceive Muslims and drain their money without a real conviction to *maqasid al-shariah* (Mustafa, 2022; Al-Rabiaa, 1989; Al-Shreef, 2005). Islamic windows are perceived as facade by conventional banks in attracting capital that are then used to support usury projects to gain market opportunities (Abbas, 2024). Moreover, according to the jurisprudential rule of "*al-Tābi'tābi*", Islamic windows are considered subordinate to conventional banks, thus are not independent in their decision making. Another concern regarding its legitimacy is also due to possible comingling between permissible and impermissible (*al-halāl waal-haram*) funds as profits gained from Islamic windows will be transferred to its conventional host to be used for its overall operations including that of the Islamic window to cover the overhead costs incurred for operating the window. Furthermore, when there is a liquidity surplus in Islamic branches, it is transferred to interest-based banks for investment and then returned to Islamic branches to cover operating costs.

The opponents of Islamic windows supported their views based on the verses in *Sura Al-Baqara*:

O you who have believed, fear Allah and give up what remains [due to you] of interest, if you should be believers. And if you do not, then be informed of a war [against you] from Allah and His Messenger. But if you repent, you may have your principal -[thus] you do no wrong, nor are you wronged (Quran 2:278).

Then do you believe in part of the Scripture and reject the rest? Then what is the recompense for those who do that

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among you except disgrace in worldly life; and on the Day of Resurrection they will be sent back to the severest of punishment. And God is not unaware of what you do (Quran 2:85).

b) *Proponents of Islamic window based on Islamic maxim of darurat (necessity)*

This group is in agreement with the arguments put forward by opponents of Islamic windows regarding its legitimacy. However, using the maxim of *darurat* (necessity), they argue that Islamic windows is permissible only if there is no other alternative (Abbas, 2024). In non-Islamic economy countries where Muslims are minority, Islamic windows operated by conventional banks are useful in serving the religious needs of Muslims. As such, choosing to bank with Islamic windows is better than interest-based conventional banks. This group relied on the following verse in *Al-Baqara* as evidence to support their argument (Mustafa, 2022):

So whoever is forced by necessity, neither desiring it nor exceeding limits, there is no sin upon him (Quran 2:173).

Furthermore, they argued that dealing with an Islamic window is better than dealing with conventional banks (Al-Shreef, 2005) but they urged conventional banks with Islamic windows to quickly move to a full conversion to become full-fledged Islamic banks (Al-Murtan, 1999).

c) *Proponents of Islamic windows*

Proponents of Islamic windows put forward a number of arguments for supporting Islamic windows. First, there is nothing wrong for Muslims to deal with Islamic windows as long as there is full commitment on the part of the host conventional bank to the provisions of shariah in all their dealings (Al-Murtan, 2005). The requirement to engage shariah scholars in endorsing the products and carrying out shariah audit would ensure adherence to shariah principles.

Second, they view Islamic windows as an indirect way of propagating ethical banking. When more conventional banks set up Islamic windows, this will help to combat usury practices in the country (Al-Murtan, 2005). Third, the proliferation of Islamic banks may encourage other

conventional banks to possibly resort to full conversion into full-fledged Islamic banks or consider Islamic banks as a transition stage (Al-Shreef, 2005). Furthermore, the success of Islamic windows can help in dispelling Western claims on the shortcomings of the Islamic economic approach (Abbas, 2024).

Fourth, due to difficulty in some countries to obtain permission to establish Islamic banks, Islamic windows serve as the sole alternative in meeting the demands for Islamic banking. Fifth, Islamic windows can contribute to healthy competition in the Islamic banking market as the competition to innovate Islamic financial instruments that are economically efficient, shariah-compliant, and meet customer preferences, can lead to a reduction in the cost of Islamic financial products (Hani -Mohamed, 2017).

Finally, Islamic windows can benefit from the accumulated experience of conventional banks to support and develop Islamic banking and increase their effectiveness, especially in countries where there is low demand for Islamic banking services, as well as contribute in enhancing financial inclusion (Sari et al., 2021).

4. Motivations for conventional banks' conversion to Islamic windows

Informed by strategic management as well as economic theories, we argue that there are multiple reasons for conventional banks to choose to operate Islamic windows. They can be broadly classified into legal constraint, economic motive, strategic motive, and organizational capability.

a) Legal constraint

As discussed earlier, conventional banks interested in entering the Islamic banking sector have three options to do so but this depends on each country's circumstances and banking regulations (Sole, 2007; Mostufa, 2006). In Western countries where Muslims are minority, such as in the EU, UK, USA and Australia, conventional banks are only allowed by law and central bank to operate Islamic windows to fulfill the banking needs according to the standards of shariah for Muslim customers. Similarly, in Oman and some parts of Africa, such as Ethiopia, despite demands for Islamic banking, their central banks only allow licensing of Islamic

windows. Hence, the operation of Islamic windows in these countries meet the local compliance requirements.

Operation of Islamic windows can also be found in countries with dual banking system like Bahrain, Malaysia and Indonesia. In these countries, full-fledged Islamic banks, Islamic subsidiary of conventional banks as well as Islamic windows are legally allowed to operate. Hence, conventional banks in these countries may choose to convert in phases starting with Islamic window operation as the legal procedure is less troublesome compared to setting-up a new Islamic subsidiary or converting to a full-fledged Islamic bank (Abbas, 2024). Regulators in these countries are supportive of Islamic finance and offers incentives to banks that provide Islamic services. Therefore, conventional banks may operate Islamic windows as a first step to support the industry and taking advantage of potential incentives available.

In contrast, in countries like Iran, Sudan and Pakistan, only full-fledged Islamic banks are allowed to operate. Hence, in such countries, conventional banks have no options other than to remain as they are or convert into full-fledged Islamic banks. Besides the legal and banking regulations, the difference in jurisprudential views of some shariah scholars on legitimacy of Islamic windows, as discussed earlier, may deter conventional banks' consideration to convert to Islamic windows to avoid any controversies with potential and existing customers on their shariah credibility. However, in jurisdictions where shariah scholars are more pragmatic in legitimizing Islamic windows, conventional banks may opt to operate Islamic windows as it is less costly but still able to meet potential demands for ethical financial products.

b) Economic motive

Conventional banks make profits mainly from credit creation and the global financial crisis in 2008 shows their vulnerability on relying heavily on such a concentrated source of revenue. Therefore, they need to diversify their revenue streams and find ways to reduce default risk and enhance stability. Islamic windows may serve this purpose. The introduction of new profit-generating products like *murabaha* (cost-plus financing), *ijarah* (leasing), and *sukuk* (Islamic bonds) reduce reliance of conventional banks on interest-based income. Furthermore, since Islamic finance is based on risk-sharing principles, it is less prone to speculative crises and ensure stability.

According to the economies of scale theory (Sirri and Tufano, 1995), revenue diversification may help banks to maximise their profits through improvement in the productive efficiency (Elyasiani and Wang, 2012) as a result of economies of scale generated by cross-selling, reuse of inputs, as well as the consolidation of back-office functions such as information technology, settlement activities, registration, maintenance and allocation of fixed costs and management overheads over a wider product range. Hence, by adding some shariah-compliant products in its offering through its Islamic window, the conventional bank may increase its profit maximization motive (Al-Atyat, 2007). Similarly, it can probe the potential of this market by launching Islamic window using its existing branch network to add to its new potential customer base instead of embarking on full conversion which is more costly to set up (Islam and Hassan, 2024). To convert fully from conventional to Islamic bank would be challenging as a sudden transformation could have negative effects on financial performance due to personnel who lacked knowledge and experience to handle Islamic products and handling of risks that may arise. Hence, Islamic windows is a low-risk strategy in penetrating the Islamic finance sector (Abbas, 2024). Using Islamic windows as a take-off platform to access the Islamic financial sector is in fact a more common practice in southeast Asia (Nagimova, 2023) and in western countries (Selva, 2023) compared to the Middle East, where the tendency has been to establish autonomous Islamic banks such as in Kuwait and Dubai (Aljughaiman et al., 2023).

So, has revenue diversification strategy through Islamic windows enhanced the profitability and market share of the conventional banks? some studies related to Islamic windows in terms of various performance measures and risk management are highlighted here. Al-Asmi et al. (2024) investigate the efficiency of conventional banks and those with Islamic windows in Oman in terms of costs and profits during the third quarter of 2022. The results reveal that, overall, banks in Oman are more efficient at generating profits than controlling costs and that conventional banks, on average, demonstrate higher efficiency in both cost and profit metrics compared to Islamic windows. This implies the need for banks with Islamic windows to enhance their cost management strategies without compromising profit generation, and leveraging the benefits derived from their association with parent conventional banks. Ali and Hailu (2022) examines the cost and technical efficiency of selected

Islamic banking windows of conventional banks in Ethiopia during the period of 2016-2020. Based on stochastic frontier approach (SFA), they found Islamic windows to have fairly better 'technical efficiency' individually and collectively; however, the 'cost efficiency scores' indicate that the banks are not efficient enough in terms of minimizing costs for a given scale and mix of outputs. Hasan and Risfandy (2021) compared bank stability between 14 full-fledged and 19 Islamic windows in Indonesia for the period 2013-2018 and came to the conclusion that full-fledged Islamic banks were less stable than their Islamic windows counterparts. This implies that Islamic windows could enjoy their market position to maintain stability without converting themselves into full-fledged Islamic banks as the Islamic banking niche market is highly competitive.

Based on a sample of 950 banks (Islamic bank, conventional and Islamic windows) from 55 countries for the period 2006-2015, Al-Ismaili (2018) analyze their performance in relation to credit risk, liquidity risk, operating risk and insolvency risk. Results reveal that Islamic bank's credit risk is not sensitive to diversification ratio compared to conventional and Islamic window banks. Conventional and Islamic window banks are found to be in a better position compared to Islamic banks in terms of liquidity risk. Furthermore, Islamic banks are relatively less profitable and efficient than conventional banks and significantly less so than Islamic windows which is probably due to the conservative operations of Islamic banks. The empirical findings also suggest that, when compared with conventional and Islamic windows, Islamic banks face increased insolvency risk.

From the above studies, it can be deduced that financial performance and stability of conventional banks with Islamic windows is much better than full-fledged Islamic banks in jurisdictions that have just introduced Islamic banking such as in Oman and Ethiopia. In terms of risk, Islamic windows have higher credit risk but lower liquidity, operational and insolvency risks.

c) Strategic motive

To remain competitive and be able to withstand the increased competition, banks must be aware on how to create competitive advantage over other market players. The entrance of Islamic banks does not only increase the size of the financial sector but also the number of banks in the country,

resulting in higher competition in the overall market. On the contrary, operations of Islamic windows increase the size of the financial sector without changing the number of banks in the country. As suggested by segmentation theory (Smith, 1956), conventional banks with windows can create competitive advantage with their presence in both market segments with tailored products serving the needs of different customer groups. This helps conventional banks to strengthen their market position by catering to diverse financial needs.

Furthermore, given the uncertainty in the market outcomes, opting for Islamic windows is a safer option as it may potentially help in gaining new customers interested in the Islamic financial products without losing customers interested in their conventional financial products (Abbas, 2024), as suggested by the prospect theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). In others words, Islamic windows provide conventional banks with the avenue to tap into the growing Islamic finance industry with less risk and lower cost.

Conventional banks with Islamic windows may not only attract existing and potential Muslim customers who seek interest-free banking but also appeal to non-Muslim customers who are looking for ethical financial solutions and risk-sharing financial models. As explained by consistency theory (Adamson et. al., 2003), through Islamic windows operations, conventional banks can gain more trust by communicating and signaling on the consistency of their products and services with the values and beliefs of their target market. Similarly, for conventional banks that have strong brand name and relationship with their customers, opting for Islamic windows can further enhanced their reputation by positioning themselves as inclusive and socially responsible through offers of ethical and interest-free financial solutions and also strengthened trust among customers who prefer shariah-compliant banking. This is in line with the consumer-brand relationship theory (Fournier, 1998) whereby banks can foster positive brand-customer relationship through positive interactions, trust, and commitment as an ethical bank.

d) Organisational capability

Within the complex banking sector, organizational capabilities play a vital role in enhancing banks' competitiveness, performance and effectiveness. Consequently, as suggested by the resource-based theory (Penrose, 1995),

banks must ensure that they have distinctive capabilities in terms of relevant knowledge, skills and attributes to enable banks to achieve competitive advantage that competitors cannot match. Conventional banks may opt for Islamic windows because they may not have enough staff trained to handle the full-range of shariah-based products that are expected to be offered by full-fledged Islamic banks that give the latter competitive advantage. Hence, at the inception of the Islamic window, the products typically being offered are safekeeping deposits (on the liability side of the bank) and Islamic trade-finance products for small and medium companies (on the asset side of the bank) which would be easier for bank personnel to understand and deal with any customer queries (Sole, 2007). However, conventional banks may capitalize on their other capabilities, such as superior customer responsiveness and technological capabilities in their Islamic window operations.

5. Consequences of increase in Islamic windows on Islamic banking financial sector

The rise in the number of Islamic windows have both positive and negative consequences. On the positive side, Islamic windows contribute to the Islamic banking industry by expanding access to sharia-compliant financial products and services to customers who may not otherwise have the opportunity to fulfill their religious commitment, especially in Muslim minority countries that only allow Islamic windows to operate but not full-fledged Islamic banks and also in Muslim majority countries where standalone Islamic banks are limited. The success of the Islamic windows will encourage more conventional banks in the countries to participate in the growing Islamic finance sector, thus providing customers with more choices of financial services to choose from.

Islamic windows also contribute to the growth of Islamic banking. Unlike full-fledged or subsidiaries which are costly ventures for conventional banks, Islamic windows serve as a gateway for conventional banks to later transition into full-fledged Islamic banks if market demand increases. Since setting up an Islamic window is less expensive than establishing a full-fledged Islamic bank, this will enable more financial institutions to enter the market with lower risk and prevent monopoly of the industry. Large conventional banks with Islamic windows further help Islamic finance to integrate with global financial markets and facilitate cross-border transactions. Furthermore, they can leverage on existing

infrastructure and capability to reduce operational costs for their Islamic windows and in turn, allow them to offer Islamic financial products to customer at competitive prices. The entrance of Islamic windows in the Islamic banking sector, drive competition, encouraging both Islamic banks and Islamic windows to innovate and improve service offerings. These innovative shariah-compliant products do not only help banks expand their customer base and foster trust in the Muslim community but also play a crucial role in promoting the overall growth and stability of the Islamic finance industry (Shahid et al., 2020).

The downside on the increase in the number of Islamic windows is that it adds more competitive pressure on full-fledged Islamic banks. Without Islamic windows, full-fledged Islamic banks have only to compete within their niche market but with the entrance of Islamic windows, they will now have to compete with more banks that have different structure but offering similar products. While increased in competition have caused the Islamic banking industry to develop more innovative shariah-compliant products that enable Islamic investors to gain access to the risk/return profiles of previously untapped areas (Dar, 2003), but they were unfortunately largely driven by the need to imitate the economic effects of conventional financial products. Haniffa and Hudaib (2010) express their concern on such activities as this may lead to moving from the sacred intentions to overcome problems with *riba* to get distorted with secular goals as a result of imitating the conventional sector. Consequently, there is now a wide range of Islamic financial products available, which offer the economic benefits of conventional products but in a shariah compliant way, a process which some industry experts termed as 'conventionalisation' of Islamic banking.

The diverse and complex nature of these innovative products require a high level of comprehension on the part of clients and also well-trained bank employees able to explain the different products (Faizi, 2024). Clients of Islamic banking product market can be categorized as idealist, pragmatist and opportunist. The idealist only considers products offered by full-fledged Islamic banks to be '*halal*' and is willing to pay credit premium as long as the product adheres strictly to shariah while the pragmatist considers all shariah-compliant products, regardless of the supplier, to be acceptable as the main concern is only to avoid any interest-based products. The opportunist, on the other hand, is sensitive to the cost

of the product on offer and is willing to forsake it for interest bearing product which is cheaper. In other words, the opportunists are willing to switch to shariah-compliant products if they will benefit them and using conventional products if they offer better deals. Therefore, effective communication and education strategies are imperative to empower target clients with comprehensive insights into the distinctive features and benefits of Islamic banking products, enabling them to make informed choices aligned with their values and beliefs.

6. Conclusion

Islamic windows are one of the three legal forms available in establishing Islamic banking in some countries. Despite some concerns on their legitimacy from the shariah perspective, especially on the comingling between interest-based resources with non-interest-based resources, the number of Islamic windows has significantly rise in the last decade compared to the early years of Islamic finance development. The paper explores the possible reasons for their popularity and classified them into four: legal constraint, economic motive, strategic motive and organizational capability. The positive consequences of Islamic windows on Islamic banking industry include contributing to Islamic banking growth, facilitating market expansion and financial inclusion, helping to attract customers who prefer interest-free banking in places and regions where they are unavailable. While the increase in competition led to greater efforts in developing more innovative products, they have been criticized by observers as they tend to mimic conventional financial products and overlooked the responsibility in serving the wider objectives of *al-maqasid shariah*.

A number of implications can be drawn based on the findings. Islamic windows have played a crucial role in the expansion of Islamic banking, offering customers more choices of financial services providers, promoting financial inclusion and competition. However, concerns about regulatory compliance and Sharia authenticity remain, and so do concerns on the products offered in the market. Nonetheless, they are a vital part of the industry's growth, bridging the gap between conventional and Islamic finance to serve wider society interested in ethical banking.

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